

When M -small modules are simple

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Abstract.

In this paper, we define and study $SMSI$ -modules. A module M is called an $SMSI$ -module if every M -small module is simple in $\sigma[M]$.

Keywords: $SMSI$ -module; small module; simple module.

2000 AMS Mathematics Subject Classification: 16D10, 16D80.

1 Introduction

Throughout this paper, R will denote an arbitrary associative ring with identity, M a unitary right R -module and $S = \text{End}(M)$ the ring of all R -endomorphisms of M . By $\sigma[M]$ we mean the full subcategory of $\text{Mod-}R$ whose objects are submodules of M -generated modules. We will use the notation $N \leq_e M$ to indicate that N is essential in M (i.e., $N \cap L \neq 0 \forall 0 \neq L \leq M$); $N \ll M$ means that N is small in M (i.e. $\forall L \leq M, L + N \neq M$). The notation $N \leq^\oplus M$ denotes that N is a direct summand of M .

In this note, we define and study $SMSI$ -modules. A module M is called an $SMSI$ -module if every M -small module is simple in $\sigma[M]$. For example, every simple module is an $SMSI$ -module (Example 2.3). In Section 2, we show that if M is an $SMSI$ -module and $N \in \sigma[M]$, then every nonzero submodule of N is coatomic. It is shown that if M is an $SMSI$ -module, then $\text{Rad}(M)$ is artinian and noetherian.

We denote the radical of M by $\text{Rad}(M)$. The second radical of M is defined to be the submodule $\text{Rad}^2(M)$ of M given by $\text{Rad}^2(M) = \text{Rad}(\text{Rad}(M))$.

Letting $Rad^1(M) = Rad(M)$ and proceeding in this fashion, we manufacture the radical series or (upper) Loewy series of M as the descending chain of submodules

$$M \geq Rad^1(M) \geq Rad^2(M) \geq \dots \geq Rad^\alpha(M) \geq Rad^{\alpha+1}(M) \geq \dots;$$

where, for each ordinal $\alpha > 0$,

$$Rad^{\alpha+1}(M) = Rad(Rad^\alpha(M));$$

and if α is a limit ordinal then

$$Rad^\alpha(M) = \bigcap_{0 < \beta < \alpha} Rad^\beta(M).$$

Since M is a set, at some stage the radical series of M must become stationary, i.e., there is an ordinal ρ such that $Rad^\alpha(M) = Rad^\rho(M)$ for all ordinals $\alpha \geq \rho$.

2 When M -small modules are simple

Definition 2.1 A module M is called an *SMSI-module* if every M -small module is simple in $\sigma[M]$.

Example 2.2 Let p be a prime integer and M denote the $\mathbb{Z}$ -module $\mathbb{Z}/p^k\mathbb{Z}$ with $k \geq 3$. Let $N = p\mathbb{Z}/p^k\mathbb{Z}$. Since $\mathbb{Z}/p^k\mathbb{Z}$ is hollow, N is M -small. But N is not simple, so M is not an *SMSI-module*.

Example 2.3 Let M be a simple module. It is clear that every module in $\sigma[M]$ is semisimple. Now, if L is a M -small module, then there is a module $H \in \sigma[M]$ such that $L \ll H$. Since H is semisimple, L is a direct summand of H . Hence $L = 0$. Thus M is an *SMSI-module*.

Proposition 2.4 Let M be a module. Then M is an *SMSI-module* if and only if every module in $\sigma[M]$ is an *SMSI-module*.

Proof. ($\Rightarrow$) Let M be an *SMSI-module* and $N \in \sigma[M]$. Assume that $A \in \sigma[N]$ is N -small. Note that $A \in \sigma[M]$ and A is M -small. Since M is an *SMSI-module*, A is simple in $\sigma[M]$ and hence simple in $\sigma[N]$.

($\Leftarrow$) Clear. □

Proposition 2.5 *Let M be an SMSI-module. Then:*

- (1) $Rad(N) \subseteq Soc(N)$ for every module $N \in \sigma[M]$.
- (2) Every module $N \in \sigma[M]$ has a maximal submodule.

Proof. (1) Clear.

(2) Let $N \in \sigma[M]$. By (1), $Rad(N) \subseteq Soc(N)$. If $Soc(N) = N$, then N has a maximal submodule. Assume that $Soc(N) \neq N$, then $Rad(N) \neq N$. This implies that N has a maximal submodule, again. $\square$

A module M is called *coatomic* if every proper submodule is contained in a maximal submodule.

Theorem 2.6 *Let M be an SMSI-module and $N \in \sigma[M]$. Then every nonzero submodule of N is coatomic.*

Proof. Let L be a proper submodule of N . By Proposition 2.5, N/L has a maximal submodule T/L . So T is a maximal submodule of N which contains L . Hence N is coatomic, and the theorem is proved since every submodule of N belongs to $\sigma[M]$. $\square$

The following example shows that a module for which every submodule is coatomic needs not be an SMSI-module.

Example 2.7 In Example 2.2, we show that the $\mathbb{Z}$ -module $\mathbb{Z}/p^k\mathbb{Z}$ with $k \geq 3$ is not an SMSI-module. It is clear that every submodule of M is coatomic.

Corollary 2.8 *Let M be an SMSI-module. Then for every module $N \in \sigma[M]$, $Rad(N) \ll N$.*

Corollary 2.9 *Let M be an SMSI-module and $N \in \sigma[M]$. Then $Rad^{\alpha+1}(N) = 0$ for all $\alpha \geq 1$.*

Proof. By Corollary 2.8, $Rad^{\alpha}(N) \ll N$ for all $\alpha \geq 1$. By hypothesis, $Rad^{\alpha}(N)$ is simple. Thus the zero submodule of $Rad^{\alpha}(N)$ is maximal. Hence $Rad^{\alpha+1}(N) = 0$ for all $\alpha \geq 1$. $\square$

Proposition 2.10 *If M is an SMSI-module, then $Rad(M)$ is artinian and noetherian.*

Proof. By Corollary 2.8, every submodule K of $Rad(M)$ is small in M . By hypothesis, K is simple. Thus $Rad(M)$ is artinian and noetherian. $\square$

Theorem 2.11 *Let $f : M \rightarrow N$ be an epimorphism and $M/Rad^2(M)$ is semisimple. Then $f(Rad^2(M)) = Rad^2(N)$ and $Rad^2(N) = Rad(N)$.*

Proof. It is clear that $f(Rad^2(M)) \subseteq Rad^2(N) \subseteq Rad(N)$. Consider the natural epimorphism $\bar{f} : M/Rad^2(M) \rightarrow N/f(Rad^2(M))$. Since $M/Rad^2(M)$ is semisimple, $N/f(Rad^2(M))$ is semisimple. Thus $Rad(N/f(Rad^2(M))) = 0$. But $Rad(N)$ is the smallest submodule K of N such that $Rad(N/K) = 0$, hence $f(Rad^2(M)) = Rad^2(N) = Rad(N)$. $\square$

Corollary 2.12 *Let $f : M \rightarrow N$ be an epimorphism and let $\alpha \geq 1$ be any ordinal. If $M/Rad^\alpha(M)$ is semisimple, then $f(Rad^\alpha(M)) = Rad^\alpha(N)$ and $Rad^\beta(N) = Rad(N)$ for all $\beta \leq \alpha$.*

Proposition 2.13 *Assume that $Rad^\alpha(M)$ is essential submodule of M for some ordinal $\alpha \geq 1$. Then:*

- (1) *Let $K \subseteq L \subseteq M$ be direct summands of M . Then $Rad^\alpha(K) = Rad^\alpha(L)$ if and only if $K = L$.*
- (2) *If $Rad^\alpha(M)$ has ACC(DCC) on direct summands, then M has ACC(DCC) on direct summands.*

Proof. Let $M = K \oplus K'$. Then $L = K \oplus (L \cap K')$ and $Rad^\alpha(L) = Rad^\alpha(K) \oplus Rad^\alpha(L \cap K')$. If $Rad^\alpha(K) = Rad^\alpha(L)$, then $0 = Rad^\alpha(L \cap K') = Rad^\alpha(M) \cap (L \cap K')$. Since $Rad^\alpha(M)$ is essential in M , $L \cap K' = 0$ and so $K = L$.

- (2) This is a consequence of (1). $\square$

Acknowledgment

"This work was supported by Quchan University of Advanced Technology".

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